

Context of Christianization and Hispanization in Philippine Music

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Article Info	Abstract
Article History	<p><i>This study aims to trace the context of Christianization and hispanization in Philippine music. The annexation and inclusion of the Philippine Islands into the Spanish Empire, which lasted more than three centuries, resulted in the subsequent remaking of Philippine society through the adoption of Western social and cultural norms. Spain became the dominant force as it intervened and directed the region's political, religious, social, economic, and cultural landscape. This study will use historical research design to identify the widespread propagation of the Catholic faith and the eventual transplantation of predominantly Hispanic culture in most parts of the archipelago, bringing the prevalent cultural and musical traditions of the Western world into this part of the world. Based on the length of the Spanish colonial administration of the Philippines and the success it had in converting the population to Christianity, and given the particular importance of music in Catholic religious life, we might expect to find a treasure trove of music manuscripts, records, biographical information, and musical instruments from the Spanish colonial period, in quantities and conditions proportional to those found in Mexico, Peru, or other large Spanish colonies. The governmental and commercial sectors should continue to collaborate to promote the vocal arts to the Filipino people and ensure that they remain a diamond with a brilliance that will be appreciated forever.</i></p>
<p>Received: November 05, 2021</p>	
<p>Accepted: June 07, 2022</p>	
<p>Keywords : Philippine Music, Christianization, Hispanization, Ethnic Songs, Ethnic Instruments</p>	
<p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6618892</p>	

Introduction

The music in Filipino Festivals, including rituals, vocal, and instrumental performances, is quintessentially Filipino. However, this event is not right. A musical connoisseur will find a fusion of Pre-Hispanic music and Spanish music. The three hundred thirty-three years of the Spanish colonization of the Philippines shaped elements of modern Filipino Festival music. It has affected many aspects of Filipino life, including music, and these influences vary in their effects among the different regions of the country. Filipinos had always produced indigenous music, varying by region and much integrated with their daily lives. There were work songs, ritual songs to control the forces of nature, as they understood them, lament songs, and songs to celebrate special occasions. Most singing was unaccompanied, although indigenous instruments were used to accompany some singing and dance. In addition to the enforced musical participation in the liturgy, musical influences in other genres flourished, including secular vocal music, religious-themed (but non-ritual) musical plays, and instrumental genres (Australian Bureau of Statistics, 2017).

Dominantly, the primary goal of the Spanish colonizers was to introduce Christianity to the country, and this was not the only goal. Filipinos of all ages learned how to sing the Latin or Spanish liturgical responses. Learning and singing responsorial, antiphonal, or unison ritual sections was a requirement for this imported spirituality. From this obligatory spiritual introduction, the foreign influences began to permeate other cultural practices and musicality of the people. Those who did not comply and acculturate were termed "Indios" or "mangmang" (derogatory word for idiots). These insults of indigenous traditions enforced compliance and obedience to the "Christian way," however people might silently resist. Although the Spanish influence permeated the arts of some country regions (particularly lowland Luzon and the more populated areas of the Visayas), indigenous traditions survived, and some Filipinos resisted the acculturated forms as foreign to their beliefs and traditions. How have these musical forms been sustained throughout the years? Despite the Spanish imposition of Christianity on native culture, this paper further argues that the traditional beliefs were still preserved through oral transmission. This allowed for the continuity of their traditional musical forms, albeit with Spanish influences (Branellec, 2015).

To a common listener, the music in Filipino Festivals, including rituals, vocal, and instrumental performances, is quintessentially Filipino. However, this event is not right. A musical connoisseur will find a fusion of Pre-Hispanic music and Spanish music. The three hundred thirty-three years of the Spanish colonization of the Philippines shaped elements of modern Filipino Festival music. It has affected many aspects of Filipino life, including music, and these influences vary in their effects among the different regions of the country. Filipinos had always produced indigenous music, varying by region and much integrated with their

daily lives. There were work songs, ritual songs to control the forces of nature, as they understood them, lament songs, and songs to celebrate special occasions. Most singing was unaccompanied, although indigenous instruments were used to accompany some singing and dance. In addition to the enforced musical participation in the liturgy, musical influences in other genres flourished, including secular vocal music, religious-themed (but non-ritual) musical plays, and instrumental genres. Dominantly, the primary goal of the Spanish colonizers was to introduce Christianity to the country, and this was not the only goal. Filipinos of all ages learned how to sing the Latin or Spanish liturgical responses. Learning and singing responsorial, antiphonal, or unison ritual sections was required for this imported spirituality (Borlaza, & Hernandez, 2016).

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Background of the study

Due to the absence of music from this period, musicological studies in the Philippines have focused on studying the music of indigenous tribes. With the pioneering work of Jose Maceda on the Maguindanao Ensemble of the Muslims in the southern Philippines in 1963, many music scholars followed in his footsteps to produce a large body of Philippine ethnomusicological studies. This left the Hispanic music that flourished in the region and practiced by nearly 90 percent of Filipinos largely unexplored. This uncharted terrain of Philippine music would find its voice only in the late 1990s when awareness of the importance of this Fil-Hispanic heritage deepened among local and international music scholars. This revival coincided with the 1998 centennial celebration of Philippine independence from Spain. It is also timely that scholars from abroad have devoted themselves to studying the Philippines' rich tradition of Hispanic music. Through his extensive research on the music of historic Manila and the Corella music collection in Bohol, Dr. William Summers led and inspired a group of Filipino music scholars to continue to work on this little-explored area of Philippine music. His yearly month-long visits to the Philippines never fail to revitalize and invigorate the spirits of local scholars to continue in this particular area of study. He was the driving force that led to a renaissance of Philippine heritage musicology. Another scholar who has made substantial contributions to our understanding of early colonial music in the Philippines is Australian musicologist Dr. David Irving of Cambridge University. Beginning in 2000, he increased our knowledge of early sources of Philippine colonial music dating from 1565 to 1815 (Central Intelligence Agency, 2017).

By the end of the sixteenth century, five religious orders were in the Philippines to accomplish the task of evangelization: the Augustinians (1565), Franciscans (1578), Jesuits (1580), Dominicans (1587), and Recollects (1606). Missionaries, knowledgeable and trained in music, were sent to the colony and brought the traditions of sacred music from the Peninsula. Music, then, became central to the communal religious celebrations and lifeways of the natives as they sang the doctrines and played Western musical instruments. Music, more than language, became the entry point for missionaries in reaching out to the natives. In fact, with the more than three hundred years of its colonizing presence, the Philippines never became a Spanish-speaking nation. However, numerous missionaries noted the exceptional ability of the Tagalogs (natives) in singing and learning the craft of music. Accounts of musical life during the early Spanish regime are extensive but incomplete, and very few musical sources have survived.

Nevertheless, the performances of *loas*, *ait*, *villancicos*, *zarzuelas*, *canto gregoriano*, *salve reginas*, *motets*, et al., described in various historical accounts have fascinated me music researchers and historians working on the music of the colonial Philippines. As one looks at the celebratory and musical practices of the Hispanic Philippines, one cannot help but be in awe of the region's intricately rich and complex musical life. It is unfortunate, though, that with the end of the Spanish regime in 1898 and the coming of new colonial power—aggravated by the destruction of Intramuros, the heart of Manila, during the Second World War—the Philippines have not only arbitrarily forgotten much of Spain's musical legacy but lost much of its musical source materials as well (COMMISCEO Global, 2016).

The incorporation of the Philippines into the Hispanic empire in the second half of the sixteenth century ushered in a new period in colonial history. Spain acquired the link that would eventually connect the world and gain control of the global trade route. This was done through the Manila galleons that made possible the economic and, more importantly, the cultural exchange of this worldwide enterprise. At the center of this global transculturation was music. Music became the most important tool missionaries used in the evangelization process as they were tasked to convert and bring the natives under the rule of the Spanish crown.

Statement of the Problem

This study is intended to analyze the context of Christianization and Hispanization in Philippine Music. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. How the Concept of Philippine Christianity started?
2. What is the beginning of Church music in Baclayon in the nineteenth century?
3. What is the foundation of Kirial de Baclayon in 1826 and its music?
4. What are the Musical Forms during Pre-Hispanic Period?
5. What are the Hispanic musical influences in the Philippines?

Hypothesis

Christianization and Hispanic musical influences marked a significant change in the Music History of the Filipino people. This study has offered the continuity and change of the musical Hispanic influences that affected the traditional Filipino mores and values of the Spanish colonization of the Philippines. Many aspects of Filipino life, including music, and these influences vary in their effects among the different regions of the country are affected.

Significance of the Study

This study has offered the continuity and change of the musical Hispanic influences that affected the traditional Filipino mores and values of the three hundred thirty three years of the Spanish colonization of the Philippines. Many aspects of Filipino life, including music, and these influences vary in their effects among the different regions of the country are affected. The discussion of the identity of a different musical genre from religious practices and festivities down to the instruments brought from Spain has attempted to resemble a representation of music considered to be among the high arts based from the inculcated idea of Christianity.

Through this, it is not a question of who plays the music but importantly the concern of how indigenous traditions survived, how the music is imparted, and performed in conformity of the culture it represents. For several accounts, Filipinos resisted the acculturated forms as foreign to their beliefs and traditions. This belief strengthens the aesthetics in the preservation of oral traditions. Indeed, I argue that though Hispanic influences in music are accepted locally and internationally, it is innovated and changed, to negotiate the identity of the Filipino people as it continues to evolve in the modernized world.

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REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

Cultural and historical dynamics in the Philippines for the last five hundred years has been one long series of continuous impingement from the outside on the most vital aspects of social life – religion, economy, politics, and education, from its indigenous and colonial pasts, different cultural traditions evolved. Among some 8 to 10 percent of Filipinos who were not initially reached by the early Christianization movement of Spain, a variety of traditional practices that are distinctly Asian in character have survived. On the other hand, varying degrees of acculturation and assimilation of influences from the west, both imposed and freely accepted or adapted resulted in greater diversification, developing new and interesting forms of social practice and artistic expression. Among the urbanized communities in principal cities and provincial capitals and towns, life has

been essentially influenced by electronic technology, industry and modern systems of education and communication (Department of Home Affairs, 2019).

It has been averred that music is the most universal among the arts in its appeal and acceptance. Music serves as a universal language that is used as a tool, regardless of nationality, to express deepest sentiments and ideals, raise awareness of whatsoever, describe, depict—and critique—socio-political landscapes. Music is immensely functional that it has accompanied mankind in his endeavors since time immemorial. As to its appreciation, music is also encompassing in such a way that one appreciates, and even loves what he hears regardless of the composer or the milieu in which the piece was composed – this is proof that music, just like all the arts, is transcendental. This is to say that it can be taken with or without its creator, giving music a subjective appreciation despite all academic standards. But of course this principle has to be dealt with on a delicate manner lest misconceptions arise (Diversify, 2017).

However, while music is universal, it is at the same time bestowed with individuality—uniqueness, that is—one that is different from nation to nation, generation to generation, and milieu to milieu. For this reason music can be said to be a collective expression of the musical genius of a particular people such that it represents their collective identity, mentality, and plight. As such, music can define a nation, and a nation can define its own music. On understanding Philippine culture, it had this to say:

*Philippine culture is not lineal. It is sapin-sapin.
And when you deal with people, Filipinos, it depends on how deeply you
go into the sapin-sapin—you'll be
encountering the aboriginal, the Hispanic, the American, and the
postmodern all in one.*

Philippine music certainly depicts this experience, itself being a facet of culture. The different periods of Philippine history are also characterized by certain musical traditions that have been implanted in the innately musical soul of the Filipino, creating a unique blend of the great musical traditions of both the East and the West. That music is highly functional is evident in the musical traditions of the country's forefathers before the advent of colonization in the islands. So innately musical was the native soul that music was unified with their daily occupations and preoccupations. Raymundo Bañas articulated how different ethnic tribes appropriated music in their social environment. For instance, the Negritos sing the *du-nu-ra* as a love song and the *tal-bun* on festive occasions, while they dance to the *pina camote* and the *pina pa-ni-lan* whenever harvesting camotes and honey respectively. Some of their dances portray the capture of an enemy or a mere battle scene. The Igorots sing the *pagpag* while pounding rice during wedding ceremonies, the *milling ayoweng* while milling sugarcane, and the *annaoy* while building rice terraces. They have the *mang-ay-tu-weng* as a laborer's song and the *nan-a-an-to-ay* as their funeral song (Dolan, 1991). The early Spanish missionaries had attested to the innate musicality of the Filipino people. Largely oral, the early Filipinos utilized music, as averred previously, in practically all occasions, capped by the chanting of their epics from North to South. In this light, it can be inferred that E. Arsenio Manuel was prudent enough in saying that—Philippinesians were easing people, singing their triumphs and woes, joys and beliefs from birth to death.

The arrival of Spanish *conquistadores* brought about a monumental change in the socio-political and cultural landscape of the natives. What once was an Eastern-oriented lifestyle now had a mix-up with the West.

The Spaniard frowned upon the native for he did not have as high a lifestyle as the latter. The Filipino was wearing *bahag* and shows off a good portion of his skin, which came to be a bit vulgar to the Spaniard. He worshipped *Bathala*, praised the mountains, the trees, and everything the nature had to offer – to the Filipino nature had a spirit in herself, a fact that did not reconcile with Spanish religiosity. The Filipino chanted his epics, which was to the Spaniard a work of the devil. In other words, the Filipino way of life was, in many ways, unpleasant to the Spanish who judged the natives from his own perspective. Despite this, the Spanish applauded, as emphasized earlier, the innate musicality of the Filipino so much that it became an avenue through which the Spanish marked themselves in the native soul.

Florentino Hornedo has published a number of works that proved the innate musicality of the pre-colonial Filipino. A number of Spanish chroniclers who attested to this innate musicality are articulated in his *Laji: An Ivatan Folk Lyric Tradition*. Also, Hornedo was able to collate sung epics from Northern Philippines published in the book *Ballads and Tales of the Kankanaey of the Bakun-Amburayan River Valleys*. *Reduccion* was an effective response to what John Leddy Phelan coined as geographical particularism (Dresser, 1996) as being the major challenge to the Spanish missionaries. With the church at the center, the previously scattered native settlements were gathered together and centralized within the range of the sounds of the church bells—*bajo la campana*.

The church at the center of the settlement also meant that the lives of the townsfolk revolved around it. This is elaborated by Juan de Plasencia who was the brains behind the *reduccion*, which served the purpose of:

...persuading the natives to settle down in a suitable place near the church and under the protection of the missionary who would teach them how to build and furnish simple human habitations as well as agriculture and other elements of progress.

This is to say that the Spanish missionaries took the burden of educating the natives in their own means. Clearly, this became a big step in fulfilling the aims of the Spanish religious to –create a Catholic community consciousness in which the teachings and the spirit of the Church would penetrate into the daily lives of the converts. This change in geographical setting brought about significant changes in the social landscape of Hispanized Philippines. At the inner core of the settlement was the *cabecera*, while lying outside were the *visitas*. And in the movement of people from the *cabecera* to the *visitas* and *vice-versa*, one has to consider the seasons and celebrations that the church has. The usual movement was from the *visitas* to the *cabecera*. This is observed especially, in times of the feast day of the church's patron saint, in other words the fiestas, Corpus Christi celebration, and most especially, the observance of the *semana santa* where the church sees herself the busiest. Phelan emphasized that:

The fiesta system and the founding of sodalities, on the other hand, reached out to embrace the whole scattered population of the parish. Although the majority of Filipinos preferred to live near the rice fields, they could be lured periodically into the cabecera village. The enticement was the fiesta. There were three fiestas of consequence to the Filipinos, namely, Holy Week, Corpus Christi, and the feast in honor of the patron of the locality. The parishioners flocked to the cabecera villages for these occasions.

Not only did the fiestas provide a splendid opportunity to indoctrinate the Filipinos by the performance of religious rituals, but they also afforded the participants a welcome holiday from the drudgery of toil. The religious processions, dances, music, and theatrical presentations of the fiestas gave the Filipinos a needed outlet for their natural gregariousness. Sacred and profane blended together. (1959, 73).

Marcelo de Ribadeneira gives a vivid example of how the *semana santa* (Holy Week) is celebrated: Most edifying was the manner in which the people of Camarines observed Holy Week. Perhaps detailed accounts of the various modes of self-denial on the part of the native converts make up the ultimate proof of the complete change in their lives. Occasions for mortification are indeed few, but it is specifically during Holy Week that these newly-converted Christians literally turn their province into one huge religious community. From dawn, starting with early Mass and Communion, the routine of these fervent natives is one continuous cycle of abstinence, prayer, and rigorous bodily discipline.

All Christian houses observe a strict observance of the Lenten season. Abstinence consists of giving up meats, and seasoning of food to remove flavors; depriving themselves of their daily baths, in order to endure the heat better; spending long hours, meditating and praying on their knees, with their arms outstretched and unsupported, like Christ's extended arms, on the cross. All idle talking, feasting and comfortable habits of eating and sleeping were temporarily given up.

A contemporary Catholic would find this attestation rigorous in many degrees, conservative, even! But this is among the many proofs that the *bajo la campana* scheme of settlement was effective in penetrating the lives of the natives so much so that Spanish traditions have been implanted in the native soul only to be perpetuated centuries hence. In other words, the traditions such as this that the contemporary Catholic still observes, no matter how loose, can be seen not only through religious bases, but also through a historical grounding. That the country's forefathers also observed these practices – and observed them more rigorously – and that these practices are still evident presently are proofs of how successful the Spanish were in their attempt to the enculturation of the Filipinos (Elicay, 2018).

But credits were not at all exclusive to the friars, or the *reduccion* itself. In fact, Phelan would attribute half of this success to the voluntary response of the Filipinos to the societal changes that the Spanish had brought about. In Phelan's own words:

Given the disadvantages under which the Spanish clergy had to operate, their efforts would have proved abortive if the Filipinos had not voluntarily responded to some features of Christianity. As it happened, the Filipinos endowed certain aspects of the new religion with a ceremonial and emotional content, a special Filipino flavor which made Catholicism in the archipelago in some respects a unique expression of that religion. In this process of Philipinizing Catholicism the major role belonged to the Filipinos. They showed themselves remarkably selective in stressing and de-emphasizing certain features of Spanish Catholicism. (1959, 72)

This Spanish enculturation of the Filipinos commenced at the religious level, the church being at the center of community life, and eventually branched out to the Filipinos' para-liturgical endeavors, and later onto their secular affairs. The development of Philippine music proves to be the archetype of this Spanish sphere of influence.

Almost everything in the early Spanish regime in the Philippines was largely done in the church, and through the church. Since the Spaniards in the Philippines were clearly dominated by the natives in numbers, to take control by means of arms would be unwise, and so there was no better way to Hispanize the country than through the church. As such, it was in the church where Western music was largely introduced. Maintaining its functionality, Western music was liturgical in contrast to native music's occupational nature. Admittedly, the Spanish missionaries proved to be adept in steering the innate musicality of the Filipinos to their own causes, mainly of evangelization (Echo, 2016).

All of the religious orders were preoccupied with teaching music to the natives, liturgical music that is. This was of course in accord with their aim to penetrate the daily lives of the parishioners to which the success of the colonization was anchored. According to Ribadeneira:

The friars taught the children how to read and write, how to sing simple songs a capella, or to the accompaniment of the organ. The friars themselves had to learn to tune and play the flute and chirimia. Some of the native boys were precocious, and they read aloud in Latin and Spanish, clearly and fluently as if they were Spaniards. They are also adept in writing, and original in drawing; many sketches are interesting. They sing in perfectly sweet and smooth tunes and are by nature, lovers of music. (1970, 349-350)

The innate musicality of Filipinos served to the avail of the missionaries as it saved them arduous time in teaching music. Credits to the teaching of music by the religious orders then natives grew more profoundly in music so much so that Murillo Velarde attests that in all towns:

There is a musical group with their instruments and singers, with which, at least during feast days, the solemn rites and the divine office are observed. And in certain places, there are excellent instruments and singers. All of these singers know how to read notes, something unequalled in the Christian world.

With this, it can be inferred that there is a certain truth about what Phelan asserted earlier that there is a special Filipino flavor that made Catholicism in the archipelago a unique expression of the religion and that in Philipinizing Catholicism Filipinos played the biggest role. Indeed, the elaborate musicality of Filipinos gave such a distinct characteristic to Catholicism in the archipelago. Among the religious orders, it was the Franciscans who were applauded the most for their musical skills and long history of musicianship (Fennig & Simons, 2017), which they generously shared to the places they administered.

In 1597, it was usual to find a parochial school beside all Franciscan churches. It was here where the Franciscans taught to sing plain chants and songs with organ accompaniment. Flageolets, flutes, and violins were also taught in primary school (Pastrana, 1965, 96). It would be logical to consider that the missionaries gave priority in teaching children so that their talents may be honed as early as childhood, and of course there is always the underlying aim of indoctrination. The Franciscans were so inclined and active in the musical paradigm so much so that in 1606 Fr. Juan de Santa Marta was sent by his superior Fray Pedro Bautista to Laguna to establish the first ever boys' choir, also known as the *tiples*. 400 boys received musical instruction from Fr. Santa Marta who were later on employed as school music teachers in their own communities. Fr. Valentin Martin y Morales, OP attested to this musical development under Fr. Santa Marta:

The Province (that of the Franciscans called San Gregorio) has the greatest desire that the natives be well instructed in music. As he was considered to be a great master in the subject (Fray Juan de Santa Marta) the obedience assigned to him to Lumbang with the mission of instructing the natives in singing and in manufacturing of musical instruments. For the purpose, the Franciscan Superior (Fray Pedro Bautista) ordered that three children from every town administered by Franciscans be sent to Lumbang to be under the direction of Fray Juan de Santa Marta. In consequence of this order of their provincial, the Franciscans arrived at gathering in that town four hundred boys whom the venerable Fray Juan instructed perfectly, not only in singing, but also taught many of them the art of making musical instruments and playing them to perfection, especially the organ which is of such an importance to a church. He composed some scores of church music and popular songs, and taught them to his pupils so that they be inspired by them and continue to develop the musical training they have received. Once those four hundred young men had been trained they were distributed by the respective hometowns with the mission of training similarly other children. Such is the true origin of the great enthusiasm and quick spread that music has in these Islands nowadays.

Historical Data and Discussion

The 1663 Constitution of the Province of San Gregorio made musical instruction compulsory. The curricular offerings included plain song, organ music, and ability to play the flute, violin, and other musical instruments. This certainly was a milestone in the musical development of the province of San Gregorio, and consequently in the Philippines, for it gave an avenue for almost all children in school to learn music and play musical instruments. Certain notable Franciscan missionaries were able to contribute to liturgical music with their own share of compositions and published works. Fr. Francisco Feirade la Concepcion composed an album for four voices: *Motetes for the Via Crucis*. Fr. Jose de la Virgen, who stayed in the Philippines from 1717 to 1767, wrote his *Arte del Canto Gregorio* in the Bicol dialect, which was printed in Manila on 1727. Fr. Pedro Parra wrote manuals, one for the religious women of Monasterio de Sta. Clara and the other a collection of *cantoriales*. Fr. Cipriano Gonzales, on the other hand, wrote various religious compositions one of which was a collection of *letanias* that was intended for a full orchestra (Fleming, 2016).

True enough, Franciscans immersed themselves in bringing the Western musical tradition in the Philippines. But it is tactless to cite Franciscan success with regard to Hispanizing Philippine music without crediting other religious orders that put as much work in teaching Western academic music to the natives. Dubbed as lovers of music, fine arts, and poetry, the Augustinians set foot on the Philippine islands in 1565 under the supervision of Fr. Andres de Urdaneta. The Augustinians still ring a bell to the Filipinos in the 21st century that is testament to their significant contributions to Philippine culture and history, all of which are still evident in their long-standing bastion – San Agustin Church in Intramuros, Manila (Geert Hofstede, 2016).

Spanish, integrated in the native character, particularly that of the Chinese. When one looks up here, one sees the magnificent sculpture-looking *trompel'oeil* painting encompassing the church's ceiling. When one looks around here, one sees the disparity between qualities of sculpture being popular and colonial. Saints that are not three-dimensional and at times frightening – this is popular sculpture. But when saints are refined, made of ivory and almost glorious to look at then it is categorized to the colonial sculpture.

As for their love of music, the Augustinians made a vast contribution to liturgical music, many of which are still very much used today. Fr. Lorezo Castelo, the Orfeo Augustiniano (Global Affairs Canada, 2014), composed the *Art of Plain Song* and the *Art of the Organ Song*, which were among his many compositions ranging from religious works, choir books, masses, and Christmas carols. He was able to use his expertise in teaching by also training pupils in Manila, the Northern provinces particularly Ilocos, and in Panay. Fr. Ignacio de Jesus did the same upon coming to the Philippine islands in 1737 authoring choir books for the San Agustin convent in Manila. Fr. Juan Jadrake and Fr. Nicolas Medina were also able to mark their names in the Augustinians' musical contribution with their *Arte de Canto Llano* and *Arte de Canto Organo*. Fr. Eustaquio Uriarte also made a name in liturgical music with his works: *La Musica Segun San Agustin* and *La Espresion de la Musica*. They are holistic, integrative, subjective, intuitive and deductive. In Philippine society, stress is given to communal relationships rather than individualism. This is thus reflected in his activities and even artistic endeavors. Fr. Leonardo Mercado, SVD calls this as *sakop* orientation.

Among these Augustinian musical prodigies, Fr. Manuel Arostegui outstood and perhaps made the most significant contribution to liturgical music. Philippines benefitted from his prominence as a conductor and composer in Spain. Among his contributions was a grand mass in full orchestra made with piano or organ accompaniment for four to eight voices. Some of his most notable compositions were *Organizations Salutaris Hostia* (1885) and *Motete al Sissimo* (1885), both to be sung by a solo baritone accompanied by violin and harmonium. He wrote the *Salve* also in 1885 and the *Flores de Maria* in 1886, both composed for three voices, the former with organ or piano accompaniment, while the latter with organ or harmonium accompaniment. In 1886 he composed his *Ave Maria* for a solo tenor accompanied by piano or harmonium. So many and vital was his role in propagating Spanish religious music in the islands so much so that he became known as the –Augusto Filipino (Index Mundi, 2014)

The case of the Society of Jesus – Jesuits – is a delicate matter to tackle especially when their expulsion in the latter years of the 18th century is considered. This may well be thereason as to why, in the parlance with regard to Spanish influence in liturgical music in the Philippines, Jesuits would seem a bit quiet. But this does not discredit the fact that they had their own share of musical contribution. In founding the *Colegio de San Jose* in 1601, the Jesuits saw this as an avenue to, like all religious orders, share their knowledge to the natives. Through *Colegio de San Jose*, the Jesuits were able to expose students to the literary-musical field. This was done through staging original and classical plays. However, the Jesuit control of the *Colegio* fell short due to their expulsion and was transferred to the hands of the Dominican fathers. The Jesuit expulsion was lifted in the first half of the 19th century where the Jesuits henceforth spread yet again to propagate Christianity with a hint of their own ideologies. It was around this time that they founded the Ateneo Municipal, now the Ateneo de Manila, in the Philippines. Teaching music to their students, Ateneo hired men from outside the order to teach piano and violin, two of which were Blas Echegoyen and Simplicio Solis (Lewis, 2006).

The Order of Preachers (Dominicans) instituted the oldest existing university in Asia – the Pontifical and Royal University of Santo Tomas. Although this may have well been done by other religious orders, the Dominicans were able to establish primary parochial schools in their respective parishes during the term of Fr. Domingo Salazaras Bishop in 1581. Fr. Manuel Rios stated that:

The king, our sovereign, orders that there be schools in all the villages of the Indians in order to teach them reading, writing, and the doctrine. The ministers of God must work zealously and earnestly in these schools. Their efforts will enhance the education and spiritual gain of their soul.

This meant that the Dominicans were not only focusing on teaching music, but were rather bold in teaching the natives in the basic tenets of the Catholic faith and the three Rs—reading, writing, and arithmetic. What the Recollects are perpetually remembered for is the innovative bamboo organ that Fr. Diego Cera finished to construct in 1822. Undergoing a series of unfortunate calamities damaged the bamboo organ—damaged by an earthquake in 1862, the bamboo became inoperable until 1872 where some of its parts were replaced only to be damaged again in 1882 by a typhoon, undergoing another general repair, the organ was finally installed in Las Piñas in 1932 (Living in the Philippines, 2016).

One might say that the bamboo organ is resilient still coming out as a jewel despite all the damages, much like the Filipino soul. Bañas eloquently describes the bamboo:

The bamboo organ is only one of its kind in the world. It is an art jewel. Its outer structure is simple, but its delicate inside parts are so marvelously adjusted that when a dexterous organist plays it, the air is filled with celestial harmony that enchants mortals.

Antonio Molina, National Artist for Music, was right in saying that the first musicians trained in Western music were developed in the 17th century for it was in this time that the Spanish missionaries were at the height of their establishment in the islands. Jose Maceda, a prominent musicologist, agreed to what Molina has averred and added that the formation of folk music was made possible through the thousands of boys trained by the fathers.

Among the thousands of young men under this tradition of vast musical training, Marcelo Adonay perhaps stood out as the best product of the musical factory that the missionaries had started. Hailing from Pakil, Laguna near Lumbang where the Franciscans taught the first hundreds of children, Adonay's emergence as a

prominent musical figure was, to Jose Maceda, of no coincidence. Serving as a church boy in San Agustin Church, Adonay later joined the *Colegio de Ninos Tiples* at the age of eight where he was exposed to western musical tradition well enough to traverse the path of music in his later years. He was the composer of many religious scores that were proof that spirituality works in ways beyond the seeing, at times it also expressed by way of the ear. To wit some significant works of Adonay: *Misa Solemne*, *Te Deum*, and *Despedida a la Virgen*. For excelling in the composition of religious music in the western idiom, Marcelo Adonay was dubbed as the Palestrina of the Philippines.

Although life in the Spanish regime revolved around the church, it was not only confined in the church, for indeed life goes beyond just religion. But so much is the influence of this religion to the character of the native that he appropriates this influence even to his authentic native mentality. With this, he blends the ethnic and the foreign in his daily affairs. This meant that the religious music that was tremendously given focus on by Spanish missionaries went outside the church. Alas, now the missionaries went beyond successful in institutionalizing the church to capture the native soul! And as for the musical development in the islands, this marked the emergence of para-liturgical music, and consequently, folk music (McGeown, 2011).

This branching-out of music that was originally liturgically focused brought about a new form of music that is called *para-liturgical*. Although this para-liturgical music is mostly appropriated in activities associated with Christianity outside the church such as the celebration of fiestas, processions, the *pasyon*, *senakulo*, *Flores de Mayo*, *salubong*, *santacruzán*, *osana*, *postores*, *panunuluyan*, etc., it could still be considered secular in nature as it reflects the native ethos and is the principal folk expression of native religiosity.

The *pasyon* is single-handedly interesting for it is sung in different styles depending on from where or what region the cantor/sis/are while retelling Jesus Christ's birth, ministry, passion, death, and resurrection. This instance is another attestation to the innate musical genius and creativity of the Filipino varying from region to region. It would be surprising to realize from a contemporary perspective that this secular realm in the Spanish era still had a hint of Christianity. This is so because religion has played so big, if not the biggest a role in Hispanizing the natives. This Hispanization was centered in the church and administered by religious missionaries – the missionaries taught the natives not just Christianity, but also the different ways of life appropriate in the West – which explains why the native character was so influenced by the Spanish that he brings this influence even outside the church (Miller, 2017).

Because of the innate musicality of the natives the enculturation of Western music – largely liturgical – became a smooth sailing affair. And indeed the natives responded with the warmest of hearts to this musical tradition that has endured for a good amount of time such that they were able to see an evolution from religious music to secular music, and consequently to folk music. Being a non-literate folk music is created by people who do not necessarily have formal training in music, very much unlike the liturgical music, which requires a certain level of musical training to compose and perform, making it essentially folk-accessible to the greater masses of people, as avers: – it is known traditionally among folk of many walks of life. Ocampo delves in this matter with more depth:

This name is given to certain songs peculiar to each country of unknown author, and which are memorized and transmitted from fathers to sons since remote times and carry the seal of that which is most intimate, most characteristic, and individualistic of each region. We must seek and go to them in search of memories, of bygone times, the most profound sentiments, the bud of rising civilizations. Folk songs, also called songs, canticles, ballads, and rhymes, reflect the peculiarities of each country, not only by words, but also by the music, as one and the other have preserved their primitive simplicity and gracefulness or their original rigor. Warlike some, others merry, ironical, mournful, animated, tender, loving or voluptuous, according to the character of the different races or according to the epochs during which they were invented by the people, that untutored, but very inspired great poet and musician (NPR, 2015).

The name folk songs ought to be reserved to those works born from the very people and preserved by traditions. It is also necessary not to confuse the folk song with patriotic songs or hymns; the folk songs form in literature and music a special genus; their distinctive character is that their authors are always unknown, whilst the patriotic songs or hymns are relatively modern and have been composed by a known author, in epochs of great political upheavals, to excite, now the patriotic sentiment, now the warlike ardor, the love for liberty or the hatred for tyranny. The habanera, danza, polka, marcha were just some of the new secular forms that emerged at the advent of folk music.

Often syncopated and performed in a slow, voluptuous movement the habanera, which developed out of the contradanza, originated from Havana, Cuba, hence its name. The English contradance form was brought to Spain and became the contradanza, which was consequently brought to Cuba in around 1825 where it was combined with Afro-Cuban rhythms becoming the habanera (Malabuyoc 1994, 91). It is set in a duple meter and is believed to be the mother of a more developed danza. As an emerging musical form especially in the 19th century, various Filipino composers wrote in the habanera form. One of which was Julio Nakpil with his *Recuerdos de Capiz* (1891) A certain Andres Dancel also composed musical scores using this form. Ernesto Vallejo's —Habanera No. 2 for Violin and Piano is believed to have been inspired by Dancel.

As emphasized earlier, the danza developed from the habanera form. Bañas explains that the danza is written in minor key and slow tempo. It is romantic and is common to the Tagalogs and Visayans. The danza also goes by the many names, to wit: danza Filipina danza habanera, danza menor, habanera Filipina, pananapatan or pangharana. Although there are discrepancies as to the similarity of the danza with the kundiman and at the same time with the harana, which are two different musical forms though they share the same characteristics, they still share the same romantic and at times melancholic taste.

Courtship tradition in the pre-colonial setting is, more often than not, a matter of showcasing physical and economic ability – a man hunts game, logs wood, goes to the family of the woman to help with their household chores, and pays the bride price, all for his beloved. But as Philippines became captive – colonially and culturally to Spanish aims, new traditions evolved and new societal norms emerged. And with music as among the main tools of this enculturation, the innately musical natives found it easy to adopt. The Filipinos moved from a courtship that caught the maiden's attention through the —flex of the muscle to a courtship that utilized sweet and serenading music heard from the durungawan that softened her heart and bent her will to finally fall victim to the man's arms – this is the harana. Traditionally, the harana is sung below the window of the maiden's house under the romantic, and seemingly intimate ambience drawn by the moon and the night. The singer (the lover, of course) is accompanied by his friends (who are also his instant teasers) playing either the guitar, the violin, or the flute, though at times these are played together. Dolores Paterno's —Sampaguita captures the harana at its finest:

*Mabangong bulaklak ng
lahi Sampaguitang sakdal ng
yumi Kung ikaw'y kuwintas nang
yari, Nagniningningkasa uri.
Sa liig ng isang
dalaga, Hiyaskang sadyang pin
ipita,
Ganda mo'y may dulot na
ligaya Mapalad ka, pagkat sa hardin ng
puso Ikaway bulaklak ng pinipintuho
At sa Bayan,
Diwa kang
pumapatnubay; Kaya'y
habang buhay
ka, Ang Baya'y dimamamatay*

*O Sampaguita!
Tanging bulaklak ng mga pagibig
Dinggin mo ang awit ng
puso Samatayo
hanggang langit*

On the other hand, Jose Estrella was able to adopt *harana* into an orchestral composition —*El Cancionero* with the subtitle —*Los Jaranistas*. Here Estrella was able to portray the steps of the typical *harana* from the start of the serenade, the journey to the maiden's house, the declaration of love beneath the window, and the journey back home (Philippine Commission on Women, 2021). The *harana* has become so popular a style that many Filipinos until now associate romance and courtship with the idea of a man serenading a maiden to make her fall in love with him under the romantic moonlight and the intimate midnight.

Similar to the *harana*, the *kundiman* expresses the lofty sentiment of love, and even heroism, in a melancholy mood. The difference between *harana* and *kundiman*, besides the scale (*kundiman* being written in a triple time) of course, is that the former is widely sung for courtship purposes, while the latter, though also sung by a man to the accompaniment of a guitar when serenading his sweetheart at night and is a passionate lyrical song with a theme professing true (often desperate) love became an important tool in continuously stirring up

patriotism and nationalism amongst the revolutionaries who constantly struggled for independence from Spanish chains during the Philippine Revolution. Christi-Anne Castro eloquently shares the same thoughts on *kundiman* as a nationalistic music:

Popularly described from a metaphysical perspective, the sentiments of the kundiman are felt to have generated from the soul of the Filipino nation and have as much to do with suffering as with hope. The kundiman is a song of passionate longing and profound love that translates effectively into patriotic and nationalistic music, an analogy made doubly potent when one compares unrequited love with the yearning for independence against tremendous odds.

The *kundiman* form developed from the earlier *kumintang*, which was originally a war song adopted into a love song, and later into a song of repose (Pineda, 2014). Perhaps it is from this origin that the *kundiman*'s nationalistic aroma is explained. Musically and textually, the *kundiman* represents some of the more significant facts of the Filipinos' psyche brought about by history and culture—sentimentality, sense of submissiveness, self-pity, yearning for freedom from want and deprivation, and the aspiration for a better future (Hila and Santos, 1994, 94). Among the many *kundiman* songs written especially in the 19th century, –Jocelynang Baliwag stood out as the most popular. Originally dedicated to a certain Jocelyna (Pepita) Tiongson of Baliwag, Bulacan (Hila and Santos, 1994, 95), –Jocelynang Baliwag helped keep the revolutionaries inspired and motivated in their pursuit of independence, earning for it another title:—*Kundiman ng Himagsikan* (REL Northwest, n.d.).

Veering away from the sentimental and melancholic *harana* and *kundiman*, the *balitaw* brings its listeners, and dancers, into a lighter and more energetic disposition very much like the Spanish *jota*. The *balitaw* is classified as a love ditty like the *kundiman* of the Tagalog whose rhythm resembles that of the Spanish *bolero*. The *balitaw* is dissected into two different forms – *balitaw mayor* and *balitaw menor*, the former being popular in the Katagalugan (Tagalog region) and the latter in the Kabisayaan (Visayan region). The difference is that the *menor* is sung as a love song and is considered to be more native compared to the *mayor*, which is more Western influenced.

This is empirically explained in the light of the geographical extent of the Spanish regime in the country. The seat of the Spanish crown is centered in the Katagalugan, specifically in Manila. This explains why there is heavy Western influence in the *balitaw mayor*. Among the most popular folk songs known to Filipinos up to dates such as the –Leron-Leron Sintang, –Pamulinawen, –Sitsiritsit, –Magtanim Ay Di Biro—some of which like the –Leron-Leron Sintang and –Sitsiritsit are continuously rearranged by contemporary composers as choral pieces and are popularly performed by various local choirs including the world acclaimed Philippine Madrigal Singers—are developed from the national dance of Czechoslovakia known as the *polka*. Written in duple time, the *polka* arouses a playful tune as if prompting one to dance and hop about. Known as a Bohemian dance, it was popular in Europe and in the United States in the 19th century, and though it had faded from the ballroom scene (as it was a favorite in Philippine soirees and balls) remnants of *polka* still exist in the above mentioned folk songs (Rey, 2020).

It was during the revolutionary period that Filipino composers emerged in the music field who consciously sought to bring indigenous folk music into the genteel art music of the period. Examples of this attempt to bring folk music to the high arts are Julio Nakpil's –*Recuerdos de Capiz* and –*Marangal na Dalit ng Katagalugan*, Diego Perez's –*Recuerdos de Filipinas* and Jose Estrella's –*La Tagalal* (CCP Encyclopedia of Philippine Art vol. 6: Philippine Music, 45). Ironically, however, a number of revolutionary songs, especially that of the marches, were highly patterned from Western musical forms. Julian Felipe's –*Marcha Nacional*, which became the Philippine national anthem later on, is an archetype of this fusion of nationalistic character embedded in Western forms of music.

Admittedly, the music of the Philippine national anthem was inspired by the National Royal March of Spain. But to say that it was the only hymn that inspired the national anthem would discredit other inspirations from which it was patterned. Divided into three, the first part of the anthem resembles that of the National Royal March of Spain, as averred previously. The second part, however, is a reminiscence of Giuseppe Verdi's –*Aida* (Triumphal March) and the latter part patterned from the French national anthem –*La Marseillaise* (Reyes, 2015). Be that as it may, the Philippine national anthem is still indeed Filipino and nationalistic in the light of the message and story that it brings—the collective experience of the *becoming* of the Filipino.

The Philippine music experience – from pre-colonial to the colonial era – affirms the maxim – Today’s natives are yesterday’s visitors – propounded by Frank Lynch, S.J., and religiously propagated by cultural historians such as Florentino Hornedo. For indeed, western music came to the Philippines shores as a foreign culture – much like their propagators with enough investment of the missionaries in teaching music, accompanied by the hailed innate musicality of the natives. Western musical influence worked like a well-oiled machine in the Filipino soul. And this learning has been passed on to countless of generations so much that this Western taste was no longer alien to the mentality of the Filipinos, in fact, it has become native itself. But this does not mean that ethnic music have been dissolved in the winds at the arrival and enculturation of Western tradition, some retained while some evolved and adopted Western forms. This creative adoption of the – visitor – in order to make it a native is an assertion of creative freedom. It is an affirmation of both *interdependence* and independence of spirit (Soriano, 1995). The Filipinos’ ability to adopt and adapt to different cultures only prove their *sakop mentality* (inclusive), while also demonstrating their individuality despite the many cultures that have melted and blended into its pot.

Although people in these major centers of population come from diverse ethnic and social backgrounds, they have developed a common penchant for foreign commodities and a concept of life largely measured by materials markers and foreign aesthetic symbols. A social order has been spawned by the introduction of western mores and ideologies to generate cultural needs which in most cases have been induced by a high regard for western life and civilization.. In the field of artists practices foreign-made music, just like its counterpart commodities in food, clothing, and machinery, has become a necessary luxury, a source not only of entertainment and leisure, but also of social prestige, based on the idea that western music represents not so much western humanism, but rather a superior quality of life. A conditioning of values nurtured for centuries by cultural emblems of western civilization in turn bred a reaction among the more literate and informed sectors of society. In time, this reaction assumed the form of nationalistic sentiments that proliferated in all aspects of social and political life from the nineteenth century through the remainder of the American colonial period (Study Country, 2017).

Philippine nationalism has manifested itself in two seemingly irreconcilable and incompatible streams of thought: one is a perceived pride in one’s capability to compete with the dominant culture for equality in all realms of intellectual, physical and materials pursuits; and the other is a concept of self-identity as a people, the attainment of which could serve as the ultimate measure of liberation from the fetters of colonialism and cultural subservience. It is within the context of the historical and cultural crises of the Filipinos as a people, as well as the broad concept of nationalism that Philippine contemporary music achieved its present character. As reference in viewing the larger phenomenon of culture change, the present writing focuses its discussion on this particular aspect of Philippine culture, its origins, evolution and present directions, as well as its implications as an acculturated response to westernization. Philippine contemporary music which in this context refers to art music-conceived compositions written or realized within the last fifty years, emerged through several stages of development in musical thought as well as a widening perception of socio-historical conditions and the rise of post-modernist attitudes on cultural diversity (Tagalog Lang, n.d.).

Concurrent with the modest diffusion of knowledge of modern art music, a need was felt to articulate in serious musical terms the nationalist sentiments prevailing in the times. Philippine nationalism in the 20’s and 30’s focused on the movement for independence from American rule and its institutional markers. In music, it was reflected as a reaction against various forms of American popular music. Classical musicians expressed strong reservations on the aesthetic values of entertainment music, and intensified their quest for the establishment of a national idiom in the field of art music. The collection of folk music and dance materials from various parts of the country was undertaken between 1934-1938, as a flagship project of the University of the Philippines under the presidency of Jorge Bocobo.

The substantive output of this field research provided the materials to develop the folksong and folkdance literature that could be taught in the entire public school and thereby mitigate the “colonial mentality” being infused on future generations of Filipinos partly through the teaching of foreign songs. The same materials provided the composers the main structural elements to “Filipinize” their compositions. Practically all important works were either based on a Filipino folk melody or bore quotations of such structures as thematic materials.

However, a lack of a much deeper perception of native musics in relation to their specific cultural and social environments as well as their functional and linguistic contexts, produced only a peripheral view of their usefulness and musical significance in the compositions. Some examples of this category of works are *Panoramas* (1931) by Abelardo, *Sonata Filipina* (1922) and *Concerto in E-flat minor* (1924) by Francisco Santiago, and *Philippine Suite* (1937) by Ramon Tapales. Even the “modernist” idiom of Eliseo Pajaro in the 1960’s, characterized by chromatic parallelism combined with modal counterpoint, derived its main thematic substance from folksong quotations. It was only Nicanor Abelardo who may have hinted on the exploring deeper the “nativist soul” imbedded not only in the melodies but also in the forms and modal constructs of the

traditional materials; e.g. the *comintang*, *awit*, etc.) The impact of avant-gardism in the next two decades further enhanced the space within which the seminal methods of grafting old melodies to modern musical framework could expand and germinate into other forms of musical exploration (The John Cooke Report, 1997).

Various concepts endemic in the avant-garde movement, such as those engendering freedom from conventional parameters of western music, provided impetus for dealing with elements other than melodies in the process of music creation. The use of different scales and modes outside the western heptatonic models, fusing the different timbres of western and non-western instruments, experiments on unconventional and unusual playing techniques, together with the adoption of compositional principles from the different schools of thought established by European and American composers, offered new areas of interest to the Filipino composers of the 50's, headed by Lucrecia Kasilag.

Writing along the formal syntactic mould of the Neo-Classic school, Kasilag combined different scales and tuning temperaments, instrumental timbres, melodic and rhythmic patterns derived from Asian and European music, with a dominant accent on Philippine indigenous and folk materials including thematic and programmatic reference to Philippine folklore. Some of these works are *Toccata* (1959) for oboe, clarinet, piano, *kulintang* and *tiruray* gongs; *The Manila Times* (2013), for actors, singers and an orchestra of Asian instruments, and the *Legend of Sarimanok* (1963) for chamber orchestra, in which she combined both 12-tone and pentatonic modes.

In spite of this highly unorthodox method of composition that has yet to define its own aesthetic parameters, Kasilag's works have chanced upon some unique sonic regions, at the same time representing an atypical thinking that is part of a whole process of indigenizing a modern Filipino musical expression. Her music as well as the music of some of her colleagues with similar stylistic orientation, points to an expanded view of Philippine national and cultural identity as one related to a larger Asian heritage, at the same time existing within the framework of a universal global order dictated by western musical tradition. One work that is highly representative of the eclectic incorporation of various Asian elements in one composition is the choral-dance work scored for mixed voices and Asian instruments. Its five sections represent different music traditions in East and Southeast Asia, with its finale focused on the Philippines. Different scales, microtonal intervals, melodic materials played on mixtures of different instrumental timbres serve as the main ingredients in the construction of this musical kaleidoscope.

The recent proliferation of various modes of scientific inquiry into the different aspects of social life has had a strong impact on the direction of evolving musical thought in the Philippines. With fresh perspectives achieved through modern methods of research in the social sciences, including ethnomusicology, previously unknown or incomprehensible properties of native music were uncovered. These new parameters of musical practice created the stimulus to the indigenization of modern musical expression. Folk music traditions in highland, pre-hispanic cultures, coastal and lowland Islamic communities as well as rural Christianized villages and towns, were regarded with renewed interest for their diversity and distinctiveness, not only from the point of view of their structural uniqueness but more importantly for their semantic properties, social functions and cultural significance. Their continued survival through purely oral transmission, without the benefit of written theories on their systems of practice (unlike a number of Asian classical musical traditions), suggested new concepts of music making (The Philippine Embassy of Canberra, 2013).

Mirroring their almost unadulterated surroundings and uncomplicated flow of life, music in these villages is expressed through natural vocal timbres, instruments of simple design, simple musical structures and un-metered musical time. In spite of traditional norms and conducts of artistic behavior, the music remains highly flexible and spontaneous. Instruments are made according to the temperament of each individual performer or artist without the artificial limitations imposed by a single standard tuning temperament or fixed sets of intervals and scales.

A concept of harmony exists not so much among the musical tones but between people, the music and the environment. An instinctive respect for the natural acoustical surrounding is observed as festivals and other group rituals are celebrated with gongs and drums, while intimate feelings are expressed by flutes and zithers. In their rich myths and epics, ritual ceremonies and other life events, an almost indistinct line separates the human world from that of the divine. In the barrios and outlying provinces, a rich variety of Christianized folk music and dances have also survived, especially among the older members of the communities. Although the forms of practice have undergone a process of hybridization and thus are structurally different from those of indigenous communities, their functions similarly enhance the material and spiritual life of the people. Their folk arts express the same attitude and respect for work, religion and nature. Communion with ritual life with all its unpredictable permutations is very much reflected in their almost unlimited capacity to improvise and modify acquired musical forms according to the people's temperament and life styles (Transparency International, 2018).

A shift of aesthetic preference from the supremacy of harmonic and contrapuntal sound complexes, precise intonations, variable sound amplitudes, metric time, and a whole notion of classicism and elitism turned into an awareness and sensitivity for simple structures, specific timbres, spontaneity and communality of musical performance, and a concept of time that is not artificially measured, but rather perceived in the unfolding and cyclic permutations of nature, related to a concept of infinity and unity with the mystic world. The rhythmic parameter in Asian music is a topic of profound interest in the studies of Jose Maceda, representing a concept of time which could be a key to the understanding of the philosophical and behavioral aspects of Asian peoples and cultures (Work the World, n.d.).

In his article "A Concept of Time" (1986), Maceda discussed the difference between structured and non-structured time as a reflection of the opposition between material logic and a metaphysical concept of life. A prominent scholar and National Artist, Maceda was mainly responsible for initiating a profound and comprehensive study of Philippine and other Asian music traditions which served as principle sources of musical thought in his compositions. In 1966, Maceda wrote *Agungan*, the first piece to use exclusively (?) Philippine native instruments, specifically families of gongs (flat gongs, gongs laid in a row, suspended gongs, etc.) Although the compositional concept of sound densities and mass structures in *Agungan* may have been influenced by European avant-gardism at the time, it nevertheless achieved a new sound environment resulting from the heterogeneous combination of sound nuances only possible in these Asian instruments.

In his later works, Maceda underscored the idea of music involving community interaction and mass participation. As a commentary on the rise and use of machine-oriented technology in order to create highly controlled sound spectra, his compositions required instead large numbers of people in order to generate sound environments that are imprecise but spontaneous and animate. He introduced this concept in his work *Pagsamba* for 200 performers and later in his *Udlot-Udlot* which needed some 500 to 800 school children to chant simple melodic patterns and play native instruments in a manner of a collective ritual act. A later composition based on a similar setting is entitled *Ading*, based on a Kalinga vocal form of the same title. In this work, Maceda also projected a concept of timelessness in Asian village life through the slow permutations of long-drawn repeated structures (Agoncillo, 1969).

This most recent repertoire of musical compositions written from the 1960's to the present represent a new understanding of musical and extra-musical resources from the traditional music cultures. It also in a way represents the Philippine contribution to a whole universe of contemporary or new music literature. As an urban cultural phenomenon, notwithstanding its competing for social space against other more deeply ingrained and more readily acceptable and easily accessible subculture emblems, it symbolizes a serious ideological reference to the present and future directions in the dynamics of musical acculturation in Asia, as well as the rest of the non-western world. While it may demonstrate the possibility of providing alternative aesthetic values and sensibilities for future musical reproductions, it has also opened new questions as to its own intrinsic values as a form of musical communication and expression within an alien environment, including its effects on the very essence of its existence. As a medium of revival of age-old sensibilities and aesthetic perceptions, its significance is nevertheless restricted by factors deriving from its own creative process, as well as the ability of existing cultural structures to accommodate and tolerate the rate and magnitude of this innovative condition. The works belonging to this style category are individualized and disparate re-articulations of separate elements from different musical-cultural traditions. While these elements possess specific values of their own, they are transmitted as mere extracts out of total socio-cultural environments and human experience (Carroll et al, 1970).

Thus, the entire body of literature may be perceived as merely representing another dimension in the westernization of non-western practices, where folk elements serve to enhance a modern idiom in the field of art music composition. For this reason, it becomes a source of alienation in an already alienated urban environment, where a confrontation between village sensibilities and oral traditions on one hand, and a sophisticated process of music making on the other, produces a unique art form which seeks its relevance in an urban mass-based culture. These seemingly contradictory conditions, having evolved and still evolving from divergent socio-cultural goals, are at this point in time converging, and as a consequence, creating highly interesting signals on future directions of musical thought and practice. While the present situation may be felt as a purely urban phenomenon, it bears serious implications on the rest of Philippine society, and has in fact started to affect the behavior of nonurban communities. By virtue of conduits provided by the facilities of modern technology, cultural institutions or urban and non-urban societies have become mutually accessible to one another.

However, being the harbingers of products of the dominant culture, urban mores, taste and modes of behavior have wielded the greater influence and control. The recent contemporary music movement in the Philippines, together with other urban-bred institutions such as musical contests, stylized folkloric ensembles and ethnic pop groups have introduced new concepts of artistic production to traditional cultural communities, the very root of their professed Filipino identity. Because of this some communities have begun to modify the forms of their centuries-old practices to conform to modern norms of choreography, theater, and performer-audience media; in the process weakening and even losing their original functionality and cultural significance.

The aspiration to achieve a national identity which gave birth to the movement and other similar endeavors became synonymous in time to one that searches for a cultural identity. It progressed through different stages of conceptualization of music creation and their attendant methods of grafting, synthesis, and finally indigenization of music composition. The multi-culturally of a country like the Philippines however would appear unsuitable to such hegemonic ideology as a search for a national or cultural identity. If ever this goal is to be achieved, it still be at the expense of all the many less dominant cultures, which will have to sacrifice fundamental philosophies, beliefs and ways of life, in order to be assimilate and synthesized into one exogenously influenced cultural mainstream.

So as not to paint too bleak a picture at the outset, we can see a number of recent positive signs relating to attitudes toward this field. One of them is the growing institutional awareness and support of this and other related fields. Before the late 1990s examples of scholarship of Western music of any kind in the Spanish Philippines could be counted on a very few fingers. The few books, theses and dissertations written at least peripherally on the subject did not include much new documentary research and there was little to add to the canon of the Blair and Robertson volumes, though a number of new and improved translations of Spanish-era documents and accounts saw limited circulation and exposure. But the 1990s saw a relative explosion of new musical scholarship, both inside and outside of the Philippines. This scholarly push was led primarily by William Summers, with significant contributions from David Irving, Sandy Chua, Maria Patricia Silvestre-Brillantes, Fr. Ted Torralba, Regalado Trota Jose and Elena Mirano. These scholars have helped to spark the creation of institutional supports for musical scholarship within the Philippines. Among these supports is the Catholic Bishops' Conference of the Philippines' Permanent Committee for the Cultural Heritage of the Church, which holds a biennial national convention on church heritage. Each diocese has a chairperson for church cultural heritage, and many individual parishes have priests, nuns and laypersons interested and active in heritage and preservation. Additionally, the University of Santo Tomas provides facilities for archival research and sponsors faculty research positions in music. More recently, the Intramuros Administration has sponsored significant events and performances.

We should note that the kind of heritage we are talking about is that which is contained in physical archives, or as permanent physical structures like church buildings. These heritage objects are inherently tangible. International organizations such as UNESCO have designated a number of structures in the Philippines as World Heritage Sites, but the dilemma encountered by such organizations whose goal is heritage preservation is what to do with examples of intangible heritage: that which can not be stored in archives. Intangible heritage is generally performative in nature and their preservation programs typically deal with the maintenance of traditional performance practices (Chaffee et al, 1969). How organizations like UNESCO handle intangible heritage preservation opens up questions of salvage ethnography and authenticity, a concept to which we will return. This is a trenchant topic in the context of the current study, which among other things seeks to revive a liturgical performance tradition while at the same time seeks to preserve physical archival material.

As far as neglect is concerned, there are two kinds of neglect that contribute to the loss of source material. One is the kind of neglect that is commonly defined as such, a passive neglect due to an unawareness of either the value of a source or of a source's preservation requirements. This can usually be remedied by the application of financial resources and/or expertise. Another kind of neglect is active neglect due to political or philosophical ideals and their incongruence with the existence or preservation of a source or the application of resources toward the same. The Spanish colonial history of the Philippines has largely been treated with this kind of active neglect, and this process is treated in some depth below. The interesting thing about active neglect, which takes a certain amount of effort and resources to implement, is that it eventually breeds passive neglect that needs no effort or resources to maintain. A good example of passive neglect is the case of the cantorales of the Dimiao parish church in the province of Bohol.

This rather depressing account should not make one assume that sacred music performance is now dead in the Philippines. Rather, music has always been an important part of the devotional life of Catholic Filipinos, and the post-Vatican II climate sparked a flowering of sacred music composition. Many of these newer liturgical works seem to have a kind of folk-song character, with many songs in triple meter that (to me) resemble some of the older songs and dances of the Philippines. As much of the cantoral repertory is likewise in triple meter and some could be considered dance-like if played at the proper tempo.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Conclusion

Based on the length of the Spanish colonial administration of the Philippines and the success it had in converting the population to Christianity, and given the particular importance of music in Catholic religious life, we might expect to find a treasure trove of music manuscripts, records, biographical information and musical instruments from the Spanish colonial period, in quantities and conditions proportional to those found in Mexico, Peru or other large Spanish colonial centers. Unfortunately, this is not the case. If we did not have a number of general written accounts of the widespread cultivation of liturgical and devotional music, the paucity

of extant sources would make it difficult to believe that such music had ever flourished in any meaningful way in the Philippines. Sources have been lost or destroyed due to war, natural disasters, climatic conditions and neglect, but those that do remain confirm the high status that religious liturgical music had in the archipelago under Spain.

These are the sources that exist, and with few exceptions they are scattered and largely incomplete. It is a rarity to find a church with a set of cantorales, an organ and other instruments, and detailed records. Parish churches that possess these things often preserve them in local parish church museums, but most churches have only one or a part or none of these things. However, the sum total of these incomplete pieces of information can provide us with glimpses of vibrant religious musical communities throughout the Philippines during the Spanish era.

One would assume that the very first contact any of the inhabitants of the Philippines had with Western music was in Mass celebrations conducted by priests accompanying Magellan's expedition. Since it is a matter of record that Magellan was able to convert a number of chieftains on his trip through the Visayan islands, we can reasonably assume that many people heard Mass sung, at least partially, though there was almost certainly not anything elaborate done such as florid polyphony or instrumental music. But these celebrations, while undoubtedly impressive to observers (as they were designed to be), likely did not make much of a lasting impression on musical practices in those areas because it was not sustained, or left in a form that could be perpetuated.

The colonial yoke was passed on from the Spaniards to that of the Americans, different schools of music and conservatories were put up in the country. Music schools were instrumental in the spread of Western vocal technique to be a part of Philippine vocal pedagogy; early schooling from teachers made a giant leap towards the development of the vocal technique. Musical schooling that once has been handled by different religious orders to accompany liturgical activities had transferred to the academe. Music became -academized during the American colonial era. This will be reinforced by the liberal atmosphere provided by the American colonial regime in the arts. Artists were able to go abroad and study there. Artists such as Luisa -Isang Tapales, Jovita Fuentes, and Mercedes Matias were trained in Italy. Although trained in foreign shores, Filipino singers never abandoned their roots. They also cultivated the country's very own native forms. These singers have trained many others to even establish a 'Philippine school' of singing and so did with the Filipino composers. In fact the first attempt to write a Filipino opera was done by Ladislao Bonus and titled -*Sandugong Panaginip* (Dreamed Alliance) that was staged in Zorilla Theater. The same composer was known for the cultivation of opera production in his hometown in Pandacan. In the absence of a theater, operas were staged in a cockpit or other makeshift stages. Also, the appreciation of the people with operas bolstered by the symphonic bands proliferated during the American period, and thus Symphonic bands also became a veritable source for the appreciation of opera music. Furthermore, with the liberal atmosphere provided by the Americans, local as well as foreign production companies have staged their performances in one of the many great opera halls around.

So while we may choose to take statements as to the phenomenal innate musical ability and devotion of Filipino converts at face value, we should keep in mind the sources of such accounts and their intended recipients, and the responses they were intended to evoke. This is not to say that Spanish accounts of the liturgical and devotional life of the Philippines are false or overly hyperbolic. This account is musically important because it illustrates the impact that Spanish liturgical and devotional music had on the Philippines in the first decades of evangelization, and on the first generations of converts. Chirino's perspective is that of a truly spiritual and committed missionary devoted to the conversion and salvation of the people in his missions.

This neglect, both passive and active, and at the local and institutional levels, has resulted in the destruction of much of the archival musical material that once existed in the Philippines. Much of this neglect can be linked to a pervasive attitude of indifference or hostility that one can trace to the treatment of Spanish-derived cultural practices in the Philippine colony at the time of the American occupation.

Recommendations

The history of Philippine music should be continued and strengthened. This affords students of both universities to get an update in the theory and application of Christianization, Hispanization, and Western on both countries, and how they conform to international standards, notably that of the West.

In the case of the Philippine experience, it is recommended that the Philippines promote more the musical and vocal arts than the way it did during the administration of Ferdinand Marcos (1965 - 1986) that saw the proliferation of opera productions and recitals. This artistic/cultural aspect has been neglected in favor of sports, notably basketball which is a losing proposition as it is a height game and Filipinos are not that tall. Finally, it is recommended that the public be provided the necessary support by the government to practice and appreciate Philippine music. All artistic endeavors will at this moment come to full fruition even without private patronage. The public and private sectors should continuously work together to promote the vocal arts to the Filipino people. They should always remain a gem, with a luster that will be treasured

forever.

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